

Occurrence of *Alectra chitrakutensis* (Rau) Prasad & Dixit in Satpuda range of Khandesh region of Maharashtra

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Abstract

Satpuda range of Khandesh region with great diversity of plants. The present paper deals with addition of a new flowering plant record from different parts of the Satpuda ranges of Khandesh region of Maharashtra is a new distributional records for the first time. The *Alectra chitrakutensis* (Rau) Prasad & Dixit (Scrophulariaceae) is reported for the first time for Satpuda ranges of Khandesh region of Maharashtra. The study provides a detailed taxonomic description, photographs and relevant information based on fresh collections

Keywords: *New records, Satpuda range, Khandesh region.*

Introduction

Khandesh consist of three districts Jalgaon, Dhule and Nandurbar. Khandesh lies at the Northwestern corner of the Deccan plateau, in the valley of the Tapti river, and is bound to the north by the Satpuda ranges, to the east by the Berar (Vidarbha) region, to the south by the hills of Ajanta, belonging to the Marathwada region of Maharashtra, and to the west by the Northern most ranges of the Western Ghats, and beyond that the coastal plain of Gujarat. Khandesh includes varied topographical features and landscape. It lies between 20^o 8' and 22^o 7' North latitude and 73^o 42' and 76^o 28' East longitude. Khandesh covers a total area of 26,703.36 sq. km. The forest of the Khandesh region is of dry deciduous type. The vegetation varies with the changes in altitude, aspect and rainfall. While working on floristic of Khandesh region of Maharashtra we undertook frequent collection tours in every season to study plants.

Alectra Thunb. represented by about 30 species in tropical regions of Africa, Asia and America. In India 3 species are reported like *Alectra chitrakutensis* (Rau) Prasad & Dixit, *Alectra sessiliflora* (Vahl) Kuntze and *Alectra thompsoni* Hook. all species are rare to the country. During botanical exploration of Khandesh region in Maharashtra *Alectra chitrakutensis* (Rau) Prasad & Dixit interesting species is a root parasite grows under shade on hill slopes in Teak forest and as root parasite on *Vitex negundo* L. collected from Haripura and Ambapani region of Satpuda range of Khandesh region. Khandesh region though botanically rich in biodiversity have not been explored extensively except a few sporadic reports on floristic of (Karnik 1959; Salunkhe 1995; Yadav 2003; Valvi 2006; Khan & Khan 2018, Khan 2017 and Khan 2019).

Methodology

Satpuda ranges, which is one of the major hotspot of plants in Khandesh region. While working on plants of Khandesh region of Maharashtra State, we undertook frequent collection tours in every season during the month of July-October to collect specimens. During botanical explorations of Khandesh region of Maharashtra state, one interesting specimens belonging to Scrophulariaceae were collected from under shade on hill slopes in Teak forest and as root parasite on *Vitex negundo* L. Close examination with the help of literature and herbarium specimens reveal that they were not recorded earlier from Khandesh region. Which is identified as *Alectra chitrakutensis* (Rau) Prasad & Dixit, it is new records for Khandesh region. The species was identified with the help of pertinent literature Rau (1961), Prasad & Dixit (1994), Mudgal *et al.*, (1997) Khanna and Anand Kumar (2007) and the taxa were confirmed by Dr. Mujaffar Shaikh, (Department of Botany, S.N.P.G. Govt. College, Khandwa (M.P) and by consulting the BSI western Circle, Pune, herbarium

as well. The voucher specimens have been deposited in the herbarium of Department of Botany, H. J. Thim College of Arts and Science Mehrun, Jalgaon, Maharashtra.

Result And Discussion

Alectra chitrakutensis (Rau) Prasad & Dixit is new distributional records for Satpuda range of Khandesh region of Maharashtra. Detailed description of the specimens is given below:

Alectra chitrakutensis (Rau) R. Prasad & R.D.Dixit in Rural Reconstruction, Ecosystem & Forestry 187. 1994: Mudgal *et al.*, Fl. Madhya Pradesh 2: 201. 1997. *A. parasitica* A. Rich. var. *chitrakutensis* Rau in Bull. Bot. Surv. India 3: 25. 1961. *A. parasitica* A. Rich. subsp. *chitrakutensis* (Rau) K.K. Khanna and Anand Kumar in J. Econ. Taxon. Bot. 31: 2. 2007. Fig.1.

Small herbs, parasitic; stems rhizomatous, underground part 2-3 cm thick, with numerous axillary buds; rhizomes orange yellow, black on drying. Leaves linear or oblong, up to 6 mm long, obtuse at apex. Flowers in terminal racemes, sessile: bracts linear: bracteoles slender, persistent. Calyx 8-ribbed, hairy outside, glabrous inside: lobes deltoid. Corolla yellow with purple streaks. *ca* 1 cm long. Filaments glabrous. Capsules globose, *ca* 5 mm across. Seeds cuneiform.

Flowering and Fruiting: September- November

GPS Reading: Lat 21.281795° Long 75.682171° (Elevation 486m)

Distribution: Rare. In satpuda ranges grows under shade on hill slopes in Teak forest and as root parasite on *Vitex negundo* L.

Specimens examined: Jalgaon Dist., Haripura forest, TAK 3275; Ambapani TAK 3309; Pal TAK 3358.

Uses: Rhizome is used to cure leprosy, tuberculosis, paralysis, oedematous swelling, fevers, intestinal worms and constipation.

Note: It can be identified by its leaves 3-6 mm long, flowers sessile; filaments glabrous.

Conclusion

We have gone through all pertinent literature (Kshirsagar 2008, Patil 2003) and by consulting the BSI Herbarium Pune. To find out the occurrence, distribution and habitat of this species. I found that, this species were not reported in any flora of the Satpuda range of Khandesh region in Maharashtra. This clearly reveals that, this species are rare to flora of Maharashtra State, even India as a whole. This species are new record to the flora of Satpuda range of Khandesh region of Maharashtra State. The voucher specimens are deposited in the herbarium of Department of Botany, H. J. Thim College of Arts and Science Mehrun, Jalgaon. On close examination of herbarium specimens and detailed scrutiny of literature published till today on these taxa, it can be claimed that these are new records for Satpuda range of Khandesh region of Maharashtra State.

Fig.1. *Alectra chitrakutensis* (Rau) Prasad & Dixit
A. Habit B. Inflorescence C. Flower

Fig: 1. *Alectra chitrakutensis* (raw) Prasad & dixit A. Habit B. Inflorescence C. Flower

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